

Paper 3

CHALLENGES OF IMPROVING EMPLOYABILITY THROUGH EDUCATION

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Abstract

Education in India is in stages of renaissance. Education especially higher education has been receiving substantial support and initiatives by the government bodies by having larger number of universities and colleges as portals to address the rising education needs of a growing population. Though demographic dividend is at an advantage in India the levels of employability is staggering over the years. Policy makers, regulatory bodies need to formulate strategies to ensure that various job seekers are able to inbuilt the requisite levels of knowledge and skills to suit the changing requirements of industry. This paper through qualitative and exploratory study tries to identify certain tangible and intangible factors within the realm of educating the youth that are required to promote employment.

Keywords : challenges, education, factors

1. Introduction – ILO has projected that by 2020, 75% of all organizations will experience operational skill gaps. India needs to create 8.1 million jobs per year to maintain its employment rate. Unfortunately, a sad reality is also wealth accumulated in the hands of a few, and hundred millions of middle class is what describes our economy today. Privileged handfuls of people are reaping the benefits of rising abundance. Inequality has risen from 81.3% in 2013 to 85.4% this year according to Credit Suisse. Economic growth needs to be inclusive and would be senseless growth if it leaves people out. It has been stated that growth in the opportunities of employment has not grown at the rate at which educated Indians are increasing in number eligible to be part of the work force, thus resulting in unemployment on the rise, despite India sparkling in the slowing global economy. Economists are also of the opinion that more work is being carried out by fewer employees, thus creating a crunch in jobs per unit of GDP. Several studies indicate that

economy has become less labour-absorbent. This contradicts the growth that India has been experiencing, so the pertinent question is whether growth itself is overstated or it is in less labour-intensive sectors or the correct data is unavailable. Job creation has to also be supported by banks and other investing institutions which is lacking. Ease of doing business in India is on arise over the last couple of decades but for it to translate into real jobs in the market would be a considerable point of time, in the interim several organisations would have to move to friendlier countries with their business proposals thus leaving little scope for job opportunities.

While we are witnessing conglomerates laying off employees who have been working with them for long, and though there is a rise in graduates being picked up from top business schools, there is a sharp decline in skill sets available with the employment ready population in the country. The pre-placement offers after internships too have seen a drastic rise in comparison to previous years. Companies are shifting their focus from mass hiring to handpicked candidates who are displaying special acumen in emerging technologies. There are several gaps that we have been able to identify on the part of the higher education institutions and universities that need immediate attention and focus to upscale employability. This has been arrived at by primary data from select employers in diverse fields and a study into their requirements through focus group studies and available secondary data sources.

2. Skill Gaps Identified -

Figure 1: Skill gaps identified in various fields

1. **Communication** - The communication and information technology field has seen that largest spurt in growth in India, but the portals of education have not been able to quickly scale up and bridge the gaps in terms of syllabus to focus on certain key soft skills as well. While here prospective employees may show case remarkable analytical and data churning capabilities, key thinking skills and creative thinking abilities are seen missing. Curriculums need to be designed to incorporate problem solving abilities, innovative thinking abilities etc. This can be done by working on simulative case solving exercises, real problems analysis. This would make students evolve thinking abilities and not just be a part of the rote study of imbibing what has been sent across without analysing and creative solving ability. Apart from thinking abilities we are also emphasising the need for students to possess simple communication skills. Soft skill programs embedded into education. Also by allowing students to do projects teachers are able to grasp and identify gaps in grasping abilities and creative thinking and presence of mind. A self assessment program among students encourages them to assess critically and think creatively.
2. **Self - Management** - employability is not just about the immediate first job, it is also about the constant need to upgrade skills and learning so as to be always industry ready. This calls for students to always be focussed on lifelong learning. The situation is glum not just in India, in a survey neither of OECD countries it was seen that, more than 35 million 16 to 29 year olds across OECD countries are neither employed nor in education or training. In his book, “Learning to be Employable” the author stresses on a set of core transferable skills, these employability habits of the mind are self-belief, self-control, perseverance, resilience, curiosity, empathy, creativity and craftsmanship. The transferable skills include communication, time management, self management, problem solving, team working, and giving and receiving feedback.
3. **Initiatives & Enterprise** - A third element of critical skills is initiative and enterprise. By this, we are looking at the individuals being highly adaptable to changing circumstances, having and displaying a high level of mobility and creativity, positive attitude, planning and organizing skills. This is more easier said than done, hence it has become imperative for industry to be more engaged in education. For this, first of all, there has to be a seamless industry –institution interface, employers need to convey what they need from educators. Second, in-work education that is, again, industry and educationists, exchange programs of students should be improved across the board and should be scalable over a period of time in relation to the need of the economy.

3. Strategies

We have identified various ways in which the above mentioned gaps can be addressed in a time bound manner to ensure enhance employability among the population of the country and employers would hugely benefit by these steps which would deliver industry ready students. These strategies are listed below -

- Soft skills programs in formal education
- Establish outcome driven learning and not input driven
- Industry-institution partnerships
- Practical application of concepts
- Continuous learning process is built into education
- Syllabus and curriculum which is constantly updated in line with industry demand
- Hone skill sets of students in a time bound manner
- Incorporate industry replica training models wherever possible
- Impetus to transferable skills
- Experiential learning vis-a-vis proposition based learning
- Action oriented teaching
- Issue based curriculum and not concept based
- More focus on applied knowledge
- Making higher education cost effective
- Skill development initiatives to be driven right from school levels
- Flexibility and choice in delivery of education

If these steps can be adapted in designing the curriculum programs and rolling out the knowledge driven programs, much of the skill gaps and issues identified earlier would get resolved for the industry and employers and quality education would be an outcome with a new meaning of being exactly defined in requirements to industry needs and will be able to cover up the deficiencies that is erstwhile faced across the best of educational institutions.

4. Conclusion

Higher education in India and across the world is seen as a step that serves a personal benefit, while school education takes the form of an exercise in social welfare to society, higher education is viewed as an exercise to enhance the socio economic opportunities that could be available to individuals and the general public who deem to need it and willing to pay a higher price for a better service. Though higher education institutions do focus on state-of-the-art

programs that involve huge capital investments as well as infrastructural facilities, it is feared that expected outcome of society in the returns expected is not met, if employability still becomes an issue. This paper studied the industry requirements and has suggested various operable approaches for universities and higher educational institutions to enhance employment opportunities.

5. References

[1] [www. Learning to be employable](#) - accessed on 16 November, 2018